

A REVIEW OF VITAMIN D IN SPINAL SURGERY

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In this review, we discuss the demonstrated value of vitamin D in bone maintenance, fracture resistance, spinal health, and spine surgery outcomes. Despite this, the effect of vitamin D levels in spine surgery has not been well described. Through this review of literature, several conclusions were drawn. First, despite the fact that a high number of spine surgery patients are vitamin D deficient, screening is not commonly performed. Second, adequate vitamin D levels will not be achieved in a majority of these patients without supplementation. Last, inadequate vitamin D levels may increase the risk of pseudarthrosis. Given these findings, we suggest that many patients undergoing spinal surgery could be treated with vitamin D supplementation prior to surgery without the need for confirmatory testing for vitamin D deficiency. This is a more cost-effective method than screening all patients. However, future randomized trials and cost-effectiveness analyses are needed to determine the ultimate effects of vitamin D supplementation on clinical morbidity and surgical outcomes.

Keywords: vitamin D, spinal surgery, outcomes, 25-hydroxyvitamin D, fusion.

INTRODUCTION

There is growing evidence that suggests vitamin D is a more critical component of maintaining overall health than previously understood. In composing this review, we found that supplementation of vitamin D has demonstrated to be protective against chronic diseases such as cancer, diabetes, osteoarthritis, and cardiovascular disease (1-3), improve immunological function (2), decrease all-cause mortality (4-5), and improve muscle function and balance (6-10). Of particular importance to spine surgeons, vitamin D is an integral part in the regulation of calcium homeostasis and bone health. As prior studies have demonstrated, low bone mineral density is a significant risk factor for vertebral fracture, instrumentation failure, and pseudarthrosis, signifying the fundamental role bone health plays in the fusion process (11-21). Until recently, although hypovitaminosis D (the accepted term for insufficient or deficient levels of vitamin D) was significantly associated with low bone mineral density (22-24), the effect of vitamin D levels on outcomes following spinal fusion were not well studied. Within the past several years, literature has indicated that patients' bone and disc health as well as spinal fusion outcomes all may benefit from correcting their vitamin D levels (25).

Physiology

Vitamin D is acquired through dietary sources and supplements, as well as exposure to sunlight. The initial form created or ingested in the body is vitamin D₃, which must be hydroxylated in the liver to 25-hydroxyvitamin D, or 25(OH)D, the major circulating form of vitamin D (26). Analysis of 25(OH)D levels in the blood is the universally accepted method to determine overall vitamin D status (7, 27-29). Inactive

25(OH)D is converted to the active form 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D primarily in the kidney, though other organs contribute minimally. Conversion to 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D is a complex process regulated by parathyroid hormone (PTH), calcium, and phosphate levels, the details of which are not salient to the purpose of this article. In addition to regulating calcium and phosphorus absorption in the intestines, 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D is crucial in bone turnover and fracture healing through stimulating osteoblasts to synthesize new bone matrix proteins (30).

Screening

A survey study by Dipaola et al (31) reported on spine surgeon attitudes toward osteoporosis and osteomalacia screening. The authors reported that only 12% of surgeons obtain a metabolic bone laboratory panel before performing an instrumented fusion on a patient with suspected osteoporosis. In addition, only 20% of surgeons requested blood testing during the work-up of pseudarthrosis. In contrast, 44% of surgeons will obtain a dual-energy x-ray absorptiometry (DEXA) scan when suspecting osteoporosis prior to instrumented fusion, whereas 19% of surgeons will obtain a DEXA scan when assessing pseudarthrosis. When questioned regarding their rationale for not screening, 33% of all surgeons reported the information obtained would not affect their management, and 24% reported the lab results would not change the patient's degree of osteoporosis. It is interesting that neurosurgeons were significantly more likely than orthopedic surgeons to obtain these laboratory tests during their work-up (32% versus 15%).

There is significant debate regarding the appropriate screening protocol for vitamin D deficiency. Whereas some believe that vitamin D deficiency

screening should be performed on all orthopedic patients (32, 33), others have advocated an algorithmic approach to screen only those at risk (34-36). Women are at greater risk for vitamin D deficiency than men; other commonly considered risk factors are obesity, diabetes mellitus, older age, and reduced sunlight exposure (37-40). However, not all research suggests that each of these contribute significantly. Thus, defining parameters for which patients to screen is difficult and may result in vitamin D-deficient patients not receiving treatment. Thomas et al (29) reported that at best, only 68% of patients who are vitamin D deficient would be identified using risk factors alone, and the only accurate method is to acquire blood 25(OH)D levels.

The cost associated with preoperative blood testing may be a deterrent to screening all patients. The 2010 Ontario Health Technology Assessment (41) reported an average cost of \$51.70 per 25-hydroxyvitamin D level and \$77.60 per 1,25-dihydroxyvitamin D level obtained. These costs resulted in a reported \$21.0 million spent on vitamin D screening in 2008, which increased to \$38.8 million in 2009. In the United States, the cost of obtaining 25(OH)D levels has been reported at \$52.53 per test (42). Although this is a relatively minor expense compared with the overall cost of surgery, the additional fee associated with screening may be unnecessary in a majority of patients. Furthermore, preoperative screening is inefficient due to the lack of a consistent cutoff for determining acceptable levels. Whereas most agree that 25(OH)D levels below 20 ng/mL are deficient, the level for "insufficient" is debated, ranging between 20 and 30 ng/mL. More recently, blood levels above 30 ng/mL have often been used as the "acceptable" range in published literature (30).

TREATMENT CONSIDERATION

Supplementation with vitamin D has been shown to significantly improve blood levels of 25(OH)D (24-26). When hypovitaminosis D is diagnosed, current treatment guidelines suggest a loading regimen of 50 000 IU vitamin D weekly, or 6000 IU daily, for 2 months. Following this loading phase, maintenance therapy of 1500 to 2000 IU/d should be continued (28). Deficiencies can typically be corrected in 6 to 12 weeks, leading to stabilization of bone turnover (31). Given that the optimum blood level for vitamin D remains unclear, the recommended daily vitamin D necessary to achieve adequate supplementation is also disputed. The Institute of Medicine recommends 600 IU of vitamin D per day for those less than 70 years old and 800 IU for those over 70 years old. However, several studies have suggested the recommended dietary allowance is not adequate to achieve satisfactory 25(OH)D blood levels, and consuming 700 to 2000 IU may be necessary to maintain blood levels greater than 30 ng/mL (7, 28, 29).

This uncertainty in treatment dosing is highlighted in a study surveying orthopedic surgeons on the treatment of hypovitaminosis D. The authors reported that greater than 45 different vitamin D dosing regimens were prescribed to fracture patients, depending on the population. In addition, the authors concluded that many orthopedic surgeons believe that fracture healing

may be improved by vitamin D supplementation but frequently do not prescribe such treatment to their patients.

Although vitamin D supplementation is not commonplace, a higher number of orthopedic surgeons prescribe vitamin D than test for insufficiency. With all other factors being equal, vitamin D supplementation is significantly less expensive than ordering 25(OH)D values, with reported costs between \$0.21 to \$1.46 per week. Given the extremely high rate of vitamin D deficiency previously reported, it may be more cost effective, if time permits, to treat the deficiency rather than to test and then treat.

Whereas the morbidity associated with vitamin D supplementation appears relatively low, the decision to offer this treatment will likely need to be made between the patient and surgeon on a case-by-case basis. Although rare, there are risks of vitamin D toxicity with oversupplementation. The Institute of Medicine reports that 25(OH)D blood levels of 50 to 60 ng/mL may put the patient at risk and should be avoided; similarly, they recommend a daily intake no higher than 4000 IU to avoid toxicity. The most common symptoms of acute intoxication are nausea, vomiting, constipation, and polyuria. Once recognized, there are many different treatment options available, depending on the severity and acuity of the toxicity.

Likewise, a flat recommendation to treat all patients with preoperative vitamin D, although seemingly inexpensive, can be complicated by numerous other implicit costs if the decision for surgery is not well planned. For example, the 6- to 8-week duration that is often required for loading patients with a weekly dose of vitamin D may have significant consequences with patient and clinical morbidity. Treating patients with extensive preoperative vitamin D therapy might be discouraged among those who are enduring high levels of ongoing pain, disability, or other costly therapies. The clinical cost of delaying surgery can also have costly repercussions in terms of other pharmaceutical therapies required to control pain, lost patient wages, and a possible adverse effect of an extended duration of symptoms.

Unfortunately, few studies have assessed the effect of vitamin D supplementation or postoperative vitamin D levels on spinal fusion rates in humans. A study by Lawrence et al examined the effect of daily parathyroid hormone (PTH) supplementation on rats undergoing spinal fusion. Though statistical significance was not reached, rats that received daily PTH demonstrated higher rates of fusion than rats who did not receive PTH.75 Whereas PTH does not replicate vitamin D supplementation, their actions and biochemical functions are similar. Similarly, Metzger et al⁵⁷ assessed fusion rates in rats with varying levels of vitamin D; rats with increased vitamin D supplementation experienced higher fusion rates, bone volume, and bone density. It is interesting that one study demonstrated that vitamin D levels improve in the weeks to months following surgery even without supplementation, significantly so in those who were deficient preoperatively. The authors hypothesized that the increased levels were

likely a result of increased physical function achieved following surgery.

CONCLUSIONS

This review of current literature regarding vitamin D levels and spine surgery has several salient points for spinal surgeons to consider. Despite a high number of vitamin D-deficient spine surgery patients, screening for hypovitaminosis D is not commonly performed. Second, adequate levels of vitamin D will not be achieved in a majority of patients with a deficiency without supplementation to their regular diet. Last, inadequate vitamin D levels may increase the risk of pseudarthrosis following spinal surgery.

Given the current literature, we advise against obtaining routine vitamin D levels in patients undergoing spinal surgery. Although it is true that a high number of patients undergoing spinal fusion will be vitamin D deficient, the utility of assessing the value before surgery is limited. By identifying patients with low vitamin D preoperatively, patients may be treated with supplementation and potentially minimize complications. However, testing vitamin D levels is costly and often unwarranted in many patients. A potentially more appropriate approach would be to preemptively treat all patients with vitamin D and continue supplementation until arthrodesis has been confirmed. Although identifying which patients will actually benefit from supplementation has its merits, from a practical standpoint there is limited benefit.

With further cost analysis, we believe there is good reason to consider treating the majority patients given the relatively low up-front expense. The average cost of a revision surgery for pseudarthrosis is \$28 069. With vitamin D supplementation, it may be possible for a surgeon to effectively reduce pseudarthrosis rates and complication expenses at a fraction of the cost.⁷⁶ Whereas many spine surgeons may be underestimating the effect of vitamin D as a cost-effective method for improving spinal fusion, a flat recommendation to treat all patients must also be weighed against other costs associated with patient and clinical morbidity. Likewise, although it does not appear to be cost-effective to screen all patients, if a patient who is prescribed vitamin D presents with pseudarthrosis, it may be beneficial to check 25(OH)D values to determine whether vitamin D may still be contributing or further work-up is required.

While these recommendations, high-quality research such as randomized trials and rigorous cost-effectiveness analysis are needed to make more definitive claims. Whereas the current literature may suggest vitamin D is likely associated with positive surgical outcomes, conclusive studies comparing the effects of vitamin D treatment are necessary to determine whether supplementation is beneficial, and if so, what dosing is optimal.

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